

Comparing three deep learning models for prediction of water levels in the urban drainage systems

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the application of deep learning models, including LSTM, TCN, and TFT, for urban water level forecasting using synthetic time series data. The models exhibited high predictive accuracy, with two achieving an R^2 greater than 0.99, and reliably reproduced observed system dynamics. These results indicate that advanced deep learning approaches can provide accurate forecasts in urban hydrological contexts and offer a basis for further development of data-driven flood management strategies.

Keywords: urban drainage system; water level; deep learning; prediction; forecasting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Urban drainage systems face growing challenges with the intensification of rainfall events. Among the most vulnerable to climate change, these systems are heavily sensitive to extreme precipitation and require innovative approaches to predict flooding (Arnbjerg-Nielsen et al., 2013). In recent years, machine learning has shown promising results in predicting hydrologic and climate variables (Dodig et al., 2024; Vinokić et al., 2025). Deep learning methods, such as LSTM, TCN and TFT, offer promising results for modeling nonlinear temporal patterns in time series data (Fayer et al., 2023; Kratzert et al., 2018; Vinokić et al., 2025). This study evaluates and compares these three methods for forecasting manhole water levels in an urban catchment in Belgrade. This study aims to assess the capabilities of different deep learning models for real-world urban flood prediction.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Figure 1. Case study with selected junction where the predictions are made.

The selected case study is a catchment area in New Belgrade (Figure 1), which covers approximately 50 hectares, of which about 70% consists of impervious surfaces. The 5-minute precipitation data from April 11, 2018, to May 7, 2020, is acquired from the main meteorological station in Belgrade, while the water levels are extracted from a SWMM model simulation. Periods without rainfall and with constant water levels were excluded due to limited relevance.

Three deep learning models, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN), and Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT), are trained to predict the urban drainage system water levels' next 6 steps based on 6 previous values of precipitation and water level. Models' hyperparameters are optimized using Bayes optimization technique. Predictive accuracy is evaluated using three standard metrics: Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), coefficient of determination (R^2), and maximum error (MAX).

3 RESULTS

All three models provide highly accurate predictions for manhole water level, successfully capturing temporal dependencies, especially for the first step of the forecast. LSTM exhibits a slight underprediction, while TCN and

TFT generate closely aligned results. As shown in , all the three models' predictions closely follow the temporal dynamics and offer a great correlation with actual values. Among the models, TCN produces the lowest maximum error of 0.0043 m, outperforming both LSTM (0.0076 m) and TFT (0.0079).

Figure 2. Scatter plot (left) and time series plot with the metrics (right) for the first step of the forecast for the three models.

Accuracy gradually decreases with each forecast step, showing a smooth and consistent decline across all three models, as reflected in R² dropping from 0.9774 to 0.8857 for LSTM, from 0.9934 to 0.8895 for TCN, and from 0.9910 to 0.8931 for TFT, as shown in Figure 3. By the sixth step, their errors are nearly identical, with TFT reaching an RMSE of 0.003 m, with both LSTM and TCN at 0.0031 m. The maximum errors are 0.0433 m, 0.0444 m, and 0.0440 m for LSTM, TCN, and TFT, respectively.

Figure 3. R-squared across time.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated deep learning methods' effectiveness in short-term water level forecasts in urban catchment. All three evaluated models captured temporal dynamics and achieved high accuracy. While LSTM showed a slight tendency toward underprediction, TCN and TFT produced closer agreement with observed values, with TCN achieving the best overall performance in terms of accuracy and mean and maximum error. These findings highlight the potential of deep learning approaches to support early warning and flood risk management in urban drainage systems.

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